

INTRODUCTORY ASTROLOGY ON SPINAL CORD

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Abstract:

The general concept of some of the medical professionals reveals that people who spent time for spirituality and meditation recover sooner from the surgery those who do not. Astrologer may be able to catch glimpses of inner life of the planet and star thereby they can guide the native for his betterment of further future course of action. Sastras say that the Earth comprises of 84 Lakhs kinds of species. Out of these, the human being is only the intellectual, intuitive and thought provoking one only. By his knowledge only, many inventions and innovation have taken place. Our sages by their intuitions and foresight could identify the zodiac, different planets and stars without having any telescopic equipment etc., For example in "Tretayuga" Maharshi Vasishta predicted about Kurukshetra war of Dwapara Yuga. He also told that Lord Krishna would preach Bhagavad Geeta to Arjuna. Like-wise different sages gave different details about the heavenly phenomena and further incidents like Grahanas, Asteroids and Earthquakes by their predictions. Our ancestors (Sages) had worked out on planets and stars, formation of day and night, seasons, distance of planets from earth and many more which are influencing on human being. They had done a good work and we are enjoying its fruits. Most of the people irrespective of their age suffering from many spinal problems.

Key Words: Bhagavad Geetha, Man as vertebrate, Origin of diseases, Grahas influence from conception to Birth, Astrology, Structure of Brain and Spinal cord, Asdro remedies, Conclusion.

Introduction:

As per Bhagavad Gita: Chapter-2, Sloka 47

कर्मण्येवाधिकारस्तेमाफलेषुकदाचना

मा कर्मफलहेतुर्भूर्मा ते सङ्गोऽस्त्वकर्मणि

Karmanye vaadhikarasthe maa phaleshu kadachana

Ma karma phala heturbhu ma te samgstva karmani !!

Your right is work only but never to the fruits thereof. May you not be motivated by the fruit of actions, nor let your attachment be towards in actions.

Man as Vertebrate:

Animal Kingdom is classified into Vertebrate and Non-vertebrate. In animals, the spinal cord is horizontal. Where as in humans vertical by virtue of our good deeds our own births as humans.

Origin of Diseases:

Our birth is not according to our own choice. We have been thrown in this world by our own "SAMCHITA KARMA" I.e., the past deeds of our previous births. If we did good deeds in the past our previous births, we will have our own comforts. If we did sinful deeds, the resulted "Janma" either by Asura or "ROGAPEEDITAA HA" suffers of chronic diseases.

Purvajanma kritam papam vyaadhi rupena peedyete,

Tha chanti hi aushadhyai he, japa homa surarchanai he !!

This we know pretty well that whatever papas (sins) we did in the past janma, the result we have to face in this janma by way of disease (here not only in the past janma, the karma we did in past we have to face it present). As remedial measures, medicine, Japa, Homa, Poojas etc., are to be performed by knowing the time of the period. The time we can predict by analyzing the natal chart.

Varahamihira in his Laghu Jataka Described:

Yadupachitha manya janmani subha subham tasyakarmanah

Pankthim vyam jayathi sastramethath tamasi dravyani deepa eva!!

The Jyotisha Sastra indicates oe show the time of plalas either subha or ashubha which are the result earned as a fruits of karmas done in the past lives, just like a (glowing) lamp which reveals the objects placed in darkness of the karmas we did in the past. It is an analization of the existence of past lives and their influences of our present life on our future ones. The stress is not on destiny or fate but one the cause and effect. The influence of the planets will be there from the day of the conception. May be this is the reason that our fifteen samskaras (Pancha Dasa Samskras) starts before the birth of the human being and electoral Astrology (Muhurtha) plays a vital role in this.

Grahas Influence:

Period (Month)	Ruling planet (Graha)
1.	Venus
2.	Mars
3.	Jupiter
4.	Sun
5.	Moon
6.	Saturn
7.	Mercury
8.	Ascendant or ruling planet of the mother
9.	Moon and final nine days Sun

Astrology:

- Astrology or Jyothisha Sastra is the branch of knowledge which explains the past, present and future experiences of human beings who take birth, live and die in the midst of the eternal space and time, Rasis (signs), grahas (planets), bhavas (houses), nakshatras are the main components which help in the three dimensional i.e., past, present and future predictions of Astrology, which are marked in the Rasi chakra.
- RASI:- In Astrology Rasi means the part of universe, which is the pathway of planets. Earth and other planets revolves around the Sun at particular velocities and circuits, through this region. There is an imaginary belt of 16 degrees spread over the space around us who live on this earth. This is called “Ravi Marga” This visible belt is the path of the moving planets.
- SUN ORBIT:-The 27 nakshatras are posited on either side of the belt. The 28th star i.e., Abhijit between Uttarashada and Sravana. Earth and other planets transverse in between these constellations. This is called Zodiac or Rasi Chakra.
- Lagna and Lagna Lord:-Lagna lord represents the Ruler of the horoscope. Twelve lagnas rise and set during 24 hours. So each lagna could thus remains on the horizon for an average of two hours. Several people would be born during this time with the same horoscope chart. The Sage Parasara describes sixteen divisional charts, They are:

S.No	Varga	Division	Chart	Area of Influences
1.	Rasi	1	D-1	Body, Physical matters, All general matters.
2.	Hora	2	D-2	Wealth, family.
3.	Drekkana	3	D-3	Siblings, Nature, courage, short distance travel.
4.	Chaturdhamsa	4	D-4	Property, mother.
5.	Saptamamsa	7	D-7	Children/progency.
6.	Navamsa	9	D-9	Wife, Dharma and relationship.
7.	Dasamamsa	10	D-10	Profession, action in society
8.	Dwadasamsa	12	D-12	Parents (Perental and maternal legacies)
9.	Shodasamsa	16	D-16	Vehicles, travelling and comforts
10.	Vimsamsa	20	D-20	Spiritual pursuits.
11.	Chaturvimsamsa	24	D-24	Education, Learning and knowledge (Academic achievements)
12.	Saptavimsamsa	27	D-27	Strength and weakness
13.	Trimsamsa	30	D-30	Evils
14.	Kha vedamsa	40	D-40	For auspicious and in auspicious effects in horoscope
15.	Aksha Vedamsa	45	D-45	For all general indications (Character & conduct of the native)
16.	Shatyamsa	60	D-60	For all general indications, (Past Karma or birth of the native)

- Each Rasi contains 30 degrees. Further it was divided into 16 divisional charts. Out of 16 divisional charts, the one used for Medical Astrology include the (1) Rasi chart, (2) Drekkana, (3) The Navamsa, (4) The Dwadasamsa and (5) The Trimsamsa.
- Rasi Chart:- It is the basic horoscopic chart. Each rasi contains 30 degrees. All other charts are only the finer sub-divisions of the rasi charts. The different houses of the rasi charts concern themselves with the following aspects.
 - First house: The heart, cerebrum, eyes. Face, upper jaw, ventral part of body, carotid Arteries.
 - Second house: Face, mouth, teeth, speech, eyes (right eye). The neck, ears, lower jaws, throat, thyroid glands, cerebellum.
 - Third house: Throat, ears (right ear), neck, shoulders, upper limbs, physical fitness, The respiratory track components that include trachea, shoulders.

- Fourth house: Thorax (Chest), lungs, breast, the diaphragm, esophagus, stoma
- Ninth house: ch, Taste and left side of the body.
- Fifth house: Heart, mind, foregut, conception, spine, spinal cord, back, Thymus glands.
- Sixth house: Disease in general, midgut, kidneys, injury, operation, the intestines, peyer;s patches, duodenum, abdomen, solar plexus, para sympathetic Nervous system.
- Seventh house: Infra-umbilical region, pelvis, hindgut, sexual union, lower spine, Uterus, organs of procreation.
- Eighth house: External genitalia, incurable disease, amputation, longevity, rectum, Organs of procreation, kidneys.
- Ninth house: Hip joints, thighs, arterial system, nerves.
- Tenth house: Knee joints, patella, Hamstrings, joint bones.
- Eleventh house: Legs, left ear, circulatory system, ankles.
- Twelfth house: Feet, left eye, hospitalization, death, toes, lymphatic system.
- 5(vii) Planets – karakatwas:-
- Sun:- Heart, eyes, circulatory system, over all spinal cord, left eyes in females, right eye in males.
- Moon: right eye in females and right eye in males, cold, pneumonia, breast related complications, kidneys, stomach, uterus, mind (maniac disorders), moments.
- Mercury: Lungs, speech related problems, mouth, tongue, hands, digestive system, nerves, cervical part.
- Venus: Cheeks, skin, neck, throat, venereal diseases and productive organs, thoracic region
- Mars: Accidents, fore-head, cuts, nose, muscle, male productive organs, bones, suicidal tendencies, lumbar nervous.
- Jupiter- Diabetes, liver, blood vessels, right ear, thigh, buttocks, excessive eating, obesity, sacral region.
- Saturn: Skinny and bony appearance, general debility, teeth, bones, joints, rheumatism, asthma, long disorders, skin diseases, tuberculosis, coccygeal nervous.
- Rahu: Leprosy, spleen disorders, poisonous injuries, snake bite, cancer.
- Ketu: Hypertensions, cardiac disorders, allergies, infectious, lunatic disorders, sudden accidents and mysterious diseases.
- As a matter of principle, the house where the lord of the lagna resides tends to prosper and the parts of the body indicated by that house enjoy good health.
- The Navamsa is the one-ninth of rasi and is equivalent to 3 degrees and 20 minutes of arc. This is the most important of the divisional charts. In general, no predictions should be made without studying the Navamsa. Here too, the condition of the lagna and the lagna lord must be analysed. The different houses of the Navamsha chart indicate similar functions as do those of the rashi chart. It has been said that when the indications from the rashi chart and the Navamsa chart differ from each other, those from the Navamsha take precedence. The Navamsha falling exactly in the eight house from the Moon's natal position has a special sinister relevance in medical astrology; this is labelled as the sixty-fourth Navamsha. When the lagna in the Navamsha chart is identical with the birth lagna, it is called as vargottama lagna, a state of strength in general. A planet occupying the same sign in the rashi and the Navamsha charts is also labelled as vargottama.
- The Drekkana is the one-third division (10 degrees each) of a sign (rashi). This has been considered as of special relevance in disease. Drekkanas have been used in some subtle manner to indicate the various body parts through adequate information in this connection is unavailable. The Drekkana that falls exactly in the eight house from the natal lagna has a special sinister relevance in medical astrology, like the sixty fourth Navamsha and is known as the twenty second Drekkana. Besides this, there are the Sarpa Drekkana (the second and third Drekkana of Karkataka, the first and second of Vrichika, and third of Meena) which too have an adverse role in matters of health.
- The Dwadasamsha is the one twelfth division (2 degrees 30 minutes each) of a sign. The Dwadashamsha chart too has been advocated for use in medical astrology. Some subtle use of Dwadashamsha is also made in the calculation of longevity. For an horoscopic analysis for disease, atleast the above mentioned four divisional charts be used.
- The Trimshamsha or the or the one thirtieth division is also used sometimes, particularly in order to understand the vulnerabilities or susceptibilities of the native, Each of the divisional chart is to be studied exactly like the rasi chart and all these charts must be studied, at first individually and then conjointly, in order to reach an integrated conclusion.

Structure of Brain and Spinal Cord:

Spinal Cord Diseases:

The human body consists of numerous tissues and organs and are diverse in structure and function, The nervous system may be divided into (a) the central nervous system made up of the brain and spinal cord. (b) the peripheral nervous system consisting of the peripheral nervous and the ganglia associated with them. The cord extends from C1 (its junction with the medulla) to the vertebral body of L1. The spinal canal below L1 is occupied by lumbar and sacral nerve roots, which group together to form the cauda equina and ultimately extend into the pelvis and thigh Paraplegia (weakness of both legs) is almost always caused by a spinal cord lesion, as opposed to hemiplegia (weakness of one side of the body), which is usually the result of a lesion in the brain. The bone vertebrae are indicated on the left-hand side (7 cervical, 12 thoracic, 5 lumbar and 5 sacral). The spinal cord extends from C1 (its junction with the medulla) to the vertebral body of L1. The spinal cord segments indicated on the right are not necessarily situated at the same vertebral levels as the bony vertebra. For instance the lumbar cord is situated between T9 and T11 vertebrae. A T8 vertebral injury will result in a T12 cord or neurological level (i.e., sensation is diminished below the T12 dermatome, and motor function is reduced in muscles innervated by T12 and below). The cord segmental levels are indicated for cervical (blue), thoracic (red), lumbar (green) and sacral (Yellow). The spray of spinal roots below the conus is called the cauda equina and is damaged by lesions below the L2 vertebra.

Astro Remedies:

The remedial measures in astrology are to reduce or to eradicate the negative impact of the planets. The ailments pertaining the body (physical illness) can be reduced by taking medicines, exercises, Yoga, Surya namaskarams, Asanas etc., This can be forecasted by the chart in advance and to some extent it can be reduced. The other type of ailment is the Manasika sickness, mental tension, worries etc., Now a days the types of illness man suffers are solely because he is living in the artificial life and not living in the nature. Our ancient sages have confronted so many problems and found out some means to remedy them. Previously Ayurvedic literature deals with Physical illness and the ways and means of curing them. The economic and social problems are dealt in our Niti (moral) and Dharma Sastras. The mental and intellectual and spiritual problems are dealt with in our Mantra Sastras. As part of Astrological remedy, I want to say about Mantra, its impact and the importance. These are the magical spells of single syllables or short phrases which, when recited correctly as well as repeatedly produce the result aimed at by the Sadhaka. The injunctions regarding the modes of their application and practice are to be observed strictly. In all our rituals the chanting of mantras is an essential feature. The Vedas, especially the Rig Veda, contain thousands of Mantras. The vibration set in motion when the Mantras are chanted, tickle our nerves and arouse them for suitable action in consonance with the achievement desired. When the Vedic Mantras are chanted in chotous with due consideration for the proper accents, he thrill cannot be explained which is an un imaginary feeling. Many experiments have been conducted by scientist on the effect of mere sounds as well as meaningful sounds i.e., Mantras. The result have been wonderful and they prove traditional claim advanced by orthodox people.

Faith is the most important to keep up the efficacy of the Mantras. The Sadhaka or devotee must have full faith in the preceptor as well as the divine power that guides our destiny. The ultimate aim of mantra practice is the realization of the Supreme Lord. When the mind, the Mantra and the Absolute being come one unit as it were, when the difference is nullified the devotee begins the experience of oneness i.e., Ekathama Bhawana.

Example: Gayatri Mantra

Any Mantra is transcendental vibration. Gayatri Mantra is the mother of all mantras, chanting this mantra has got benefits to the person who chants regularly. It removes all the obstacles in our life.

- It protects us from any kind of danger.
- Improves our memory power, the Transcendental Vibration increases our intellectual power.
- It increases concentration, learning power and increase our creativity.
- It increases our overall health and wealth.
- It increases our vitality and beauty.
- It attains ultimate peace in our mind and body.

Conclusion:

During pregnancy of 2nd month, neural tube (brain, spinal cord and the other neural tubes of the central nervous system) is well formed (week 5th to 8th). The ruling planet for 2nd month of pregnancy is "MARS". There-fore in this month Mars propitiative measures are advocated. As spinal cord is main organ of the communicative system of nervous net work between brain and the physical body; astrological guidance is needed to be free from Epidemic, pandemic and the other physiological disorders of dreadful consequences.

References:

1. Jyotirvydyam an article by Dr. Srinivas Phanindra Adiraju.
2. Subtleties of Medical Astrology by Dr.K.S. Charak, M.S.(Surgery)FRCS. UK Editor Vedic Astrology, Uma publications, Delhi
3. Human Neuroanatomy, 5th edition, Inder Bir Singh, M,S, Phd., FAMS, Jaypee Brothers, Medical Publishers (p) Ltd., New Delhi
4. M.facebook.compastroritest.
5. Potti Sri Ramulu Telugu University Publications.
6. Parasara Hora Sastra.